

WHEN SOME THINGS ARE MISSING: GAPS OF INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION IN GOOGLE CLASSROOM

Marjorey C. Cabigas, DA ¹
Domie C. Mata, Jr., EdD ²

¹ *J.H. Cerilles State College – Dumingag Campus, Zamboanga del Sur*

² *San Jose Elementary School, Pagadian City, Zamboanga del Sur*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816010>

ABSTRACT

This study looks into Google Classroom's interpersonal communication gaps between the educator and the students. The study's specific objectives are to: recognize the medium, establish the interface, evaluate the caliber of instruction, and develop E.M.-based standards for interpersonal contact in the Google Classroom, Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action, which serves as a sub theory and is supported by Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory. The results show that there is a communication gap between the teacher and the students in Google Classroom. The following suggestions are made based on the summary of findings: investigate how the medium is identified in the teaching and learning process in virtual classrooms as a gap in relationships; look into how the interface is determined and how it functions as a barrier to or gap in interpersonal communication; evaluate the caliber of instruction and how it affects students' learning in virtual classrooms as a gap in interpersonal communication; and the action plan may focus on medium identification, interface determination, quality of education and its impact to students learning.

Keywords: *gaps, Google Classroom, interface, interpersonal communication, medium*

INTRODUCTION

Online education is quickly becoming one of the most affordable methods for educating the world's fastest-growing workforce (Messman, 2021).

The educational landscape is permanently changed when the COVID-19 outbreak spreads across the globe. Public and private educational institutions searched for the most effective and efficient Learning Management System (LMS) to satisfy the needs of the students. Since education is provided online by faculty and occurs the manner of real-time (synchronous) and at all times (asynchronous) interactions, this led to the use of social media systems and virtual reality in distance learning. However, difficulties arise from a lack of time and resources to adequately prepare for online education. Many institutions of higher learning are still searching for a low-cost, simple-to-use learning management system (LMS) to assist them in addressing the nation's current online education problems.

As the COVID-19 pandemic propagates across the globe, the Google Classroom is a type of learning management system (LMS) that aims to make the creation, distribution, and evaluation of assignments along with that include students in distance education easier. Google Classroom is a free service designed to let students and teachers communicate, collaborate, manage assignments, go electronic format, and much more. It was added as a feature to Google Apps for Education on August 12, 2014, after becoming generally accessible (Flynn and Lutz). Google Classroom uses a modest quantity of data and does not demand powerful technology. As a virtual reality tool, this platform can therefore be of considerable assistance to the academic community in addressing the difficulties associated with online education in the Philippines.

A worthwhile and efficient teaching and learning process requires interpersonal contact (Jouany & Martic, 2020). The most important need is that a message be there, transmitted by the sender, and received by the recipient. However, interpersonal communication gaps were a struggle for both students and teachers. Teachers made every effort to get in touch with and find kids they did not even know. The pupils were worried that the teachers would get in touch with them and add them to a class of strangers where interpersonal communication problems could prevent them from studying well (Harappa Diaries, 2021). Even the Commission on Higher degree provided flexible learning options, but some courses demand online or in-person instruction to receive a decent degree.

Thus, this study investigates the gaps of interpersonal communication between the teacher and the students in Google Classroom by considering medium, interface and quality of education as sub-problems of the study. Drawing inferences from empirical evidences is done to demonstrate understanding of the problems under study. Finally, a guideline in interpersonal communication in Google Classroom is crafted.

METHODOLOGY

Discourse analysis is one of the qualitative techniques used in this study. The qualitative method analyzes the meanings developed through language use in interpersonal interaction, the settings and procedures of these ideas and practices, rather than using numerical analysis. Discourse analysis is a technique for examining the use of language in the context of its social setting and tries to comprehend how language is utilized in everyday situations. Specifically, this study investigates the gaps in interpersonal communication between the teacher and the students in Google Classroom using medium, interface and quality of education guided by E.M. Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory that stands as the main theory and supported by the sub-theories of Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action, Edward Giles' Communication Accommodation Theory, and Jesse Delia's Constructivism Theory.

The main source of data is from the archive of an assistant professor in a state college in the Philippines in which the Google Classroom was used as a teacher and as a student. The secondary sources of data include magazines, newspapers, books and internet.

In response to the three sub-problems raised in the study; the procedure of investigation follows three phases: Phase 1. Medium Identification, Phase 2. Interface Determine, and Phase 3. Quality of Education Analysis.

Phase 1. Medium Identification.

This phase identifies the medium of learning used in the teaching and learning process with Google Classroom as the virtual platform to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication by John Wallen.

Table 1. Medium.

Medium Used	Teaching and Learning Process	Gaps of Interpersonal Communication
Lecture		
Video		
Power point Presentation		
Literary Criticism		

Phase 2. Interface Determination.

This phase establishes the interface utilized during the method of delivery of education by instructor in the Google Classroom as a prerequisite for submissions from the students in order to find the gaps in interpersonal interaction and the interface used, such as cognitive artifacts, the instructional materials in the educational setting, and the occasions for learning, using John Wallen's model.

Table 2. Interface.

Interface	Requirements for Submission	Gaps of Interpersonal Communication
Cognitive artifacts		
Resources for learning		
Occasion for learning		

Phase 3. Quality of Education Analysis.

This phase analyzes the quality of education making use of student's outputs and submissions in the Google Classroom to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication in a paragraph discourse analysis.

Data Analysis

This study investigates the gaps in interpersonal communication between the teacher and the students in Google Classroom using medium, interface and quality of education guided by E.M. Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory that stands as the main theory and supported by the sub-theories of Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen's Theory of Reasoned Action, Edward Giles' Communication Accommodation Theory, and Jesse Delia's Constructivism Theory. Phase 1 of the learning process involves choosing the learning medium, which can be visual, tactile, aural, or a combination of these, to be used in the course of instruction and learning using Google Classroom as the online platform. Phase 2 involves choosing the interface to be used, such as cognitive artifacts, learning resources in the educational setting, and occasions for learning in the method of delivery of teaching by instructor in the Google Classroom as well as the student' participation requirements. Phase 3 is the analysis of the quality of education making use of student's outputs and submissions in the Google Classroom to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication in a paragraph discourse analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The study is purely discourse analysis of a Google Classroom archive of an assistant professor in a state college in the Philippines. The participant as the owner of the account is fully aware that the discourses are used only for research purposes and not to be disclosed publicly, the anonymity is maintained and informed consent is obtained. The participant is also free to withdraw from the study anytime, the well-being is safeguarded and there is no conflict of interest that exist in the study. Most of all, the study strictly avoided plagiarism and there is no bias in the interpretation of the findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Medium Identification

Table 1 shows the identification on the medium of learning used in the teaching and learning process with Google Classroom as the virtual platform to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication by John Wallen.

Table 1. Medium Identification Analysis

Medium Used	Teaching and Learning Process	Gaps of Interpersonal Communication
Lecture	Assigned Report (individual and/or group)	Intention
Video	Oral/Speaking Requirements	Action
Power point Presentation	Reporting/Lecture Presentation	Intention
Literary Criticism	Final Exam Requirement	Impact

The table identifies the medium of learning used in the teaching and learning process with Google Classroom as the virtual platform to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication.

Google is a popular Web 2.0 tool that offers a variety of practical functions and applications. Like many other Web 2.0 apps, it has many possibilities for teaching and learning thanks to its unique built-in features that offer educational, social, and scientific affordances. 2014 saw the addition of Google Classroom as a new component of Google Apps for Education. The professors may quickly assign projects, provide feedback, and engage with the students in this classroom (Flynn and Lutz).

Google Classroom can accommodate different medium which the teacher prefers depending on the course assigned which can make the teaching and learning process easier but still there are gaps in interpersonal communication such as intention, action and impact that need consideration.

Intention is very clear when the teacher explains the rubrics and criteria to be used in the delivery of assigned topics for the reporting which is individual or by group as well as the use of power point presentation as aid in the lecture and oral presentation for the students to follow and comply. However, due to intermittent to slow internet connection students will not be able to get and digest the proper way to make it and sometimes tend to have done it the other way around. Google Classroom is a useful tool for promoting efficient methods of instruction and learning due to its simplicity to utilize and intended function. Using the Classroom feature of Google as an intellectual/pedagogical tool for imparting knowledge and understanding how to evaluate data and related applications is the purpose of the program (Nizal, Shaharane, Jamil, and Rodzi, 2014).

Action is manifested when a student is able to apply things and elements in the required video presentation as one of the outputs needed in a particular course as to what is asked as to guidelines, mechanics and rubrics. However, due to no gadget available some students cannot submit videos and teachers need to think of other things to comply that can suffice a video presentation, to do it face to face, live and personal but following the health protocols. The teacher's difficult tasks are to guarantee that pupils believe it is simple to use and that they are aware of its use in instruction. Google Classroom can be enhanced to become a portion shown/cognitive tool to assist in shifting the focus of the educational setting from one that is organized around teachers and handled to one that is student-centered and open to the purpose of discussion, examination, and imaginative thinking through the participation of students who are engaged individuals. "All channels have been evaluated as a way of interpersonal relationships," writes Palmer.

Impact is evident when a student is able to apply the learned information, skills and values needed in the completion of the final exam requirement. Somehow, students need samples to do what is asked when they cannot join the live discussion or are in and out of the virtual discussion due to intermittent to slow internet connection, the need for hard copies to those with no gadgets and preferred the printed modules and influx of private messages, chats and even emails on the elaboration of the requirement to do. These gaps are simply noticeable especially in this technology aid learning that underprivileged students cannot cope with.

Virtual Reality (VR) communication, according to S. R. Ellis (2018), is a media that uses virtual settings to depict communication. It is expected to become the next dominating medium, if not the final one. Due to the notion of a technology for communications typically assumes that two or more people are participating, the terms "communication" and a "medium ought to only be applied in the context of shared VR. Interpersonal communication, according to Stasser (2018), is the process through which an ensemble of social actors in a particular circumstance negotiates the significance of the numerous situations that develop between them. If it is true that interaction between individuals is a method of negotiation, eventually this definition has important ramifications: (1) the only way to understand is by evaluating the subjects who engage in a manner in which the social environment whereby the interaction with virtual reality occurs plays a vital part; and (2) new procedures and operations will emerge during relationship that compromise and adapt the initial connection between subject matter and the context. In other words, whether or not they are proficient computer users, individuals act autonomously and have their own motivations, and it is up to computers and systems to adapt to people rather than the other way around.

The gaps in interpersonal communication found in medium identification are intention, action and impact.

Interface Determination

Table 2 determines the interface used to identify the gaps in interpersonal communication and the interface used, such as cognitive artifacts, the resources for

learning in the learning environment, and the occasion for studying in the method of education by the teacher in the Google Classroom as student's expectations for submissions.

Table 2. Interface Determination Analysis

Interface	Requirements for Submission	Gaps of Interpersonal Communication
Cognitive artifacts	Essays (Reflection and Reaction Paper)	Intention
Resources for learning	Online Materials such as Videos, Movies, E-books	Impact
Occasion for learning	Midterm, Final Exam	Action

Table 2 determines the interface used in the delivery of instruction by the teacher in the Google Classroom as student's requirements for submissions to identify the gaps in interpersonal communication and the interface used such as cognitive artifacts, the resources for learning in the learning environment and occasion for learning in the delivery of instruction by the teacher in the Google Classroom as student's requirements for submissions.

Application Programming Interface (API), which comprises a collection of definitions and protocols for development and integration of application software, is a feature of Google Classroom. Using the API, G Suite for Education domain administrators may link student information systems with Classroom, systematically provision steps on behalf of teachers, and gain a basic understanding of the classes being taught in the domain. To link apps with Classroom, creators of applications may utilize the Classroom API. To ask teachers for permission to access classes and rosters, the apps must use OAuth 2.0. Administrators have stated that students and educators within the domain are not permitted to grant applications accessibility to Google Classroom data. Website administrators and content producers can help learners and educators share materials back to Classroom by using the share button. All API and share button connections should adhere to the class brand rules. The various types of entities in the Classroom API serve as representations for the courses, teachers, and students on the interface. In addition to the attributes seen in Classroom, some of these things also have extra properties that are exclusive to the API. According to the Google Classroom API, the main entity types include classes, disguises, invitations, learners, instructors, profiles of users, instruction, topics, and student responses (Google Classroom API).

Intention is seen as an imbalance in communication among cognitive artifacts, especially in essay writing (reflection and response papers), when students will just look up online resources to submit in the belief that the teacher in charge of the assignment won't catch them. Writing is one of the tedious skills in a literature and communication courses however the students tend to forget that there is also plagiarism scanner application that will detect if it is copied or original. The intention was purely to train students to write good composition and articles but it was not achieved due to easy ways

to operate the internet nowadays. Sometimes students will only ask from their classmates the article and just change the font size, even the layout then automatically turn in as submission in the Google Classroom. According to Augustine and Abraham (2021), which measured students' communication ability levels in Google Classroom, those levels increased and were noticeably higher as an outcome of the tutorials on how to use Google Classroom. However, there were no appreciable gender differences in the students' Google Classroom interpersonal levels.

Impact is apparent as a gap in interpersonal communication in the resources for learning specifically on the online materials used such as videos, movies, e-books. The materials should be watched and studied by the teacher before giving that to the students, upload as attachment in the Google Classroom and explained why the materials are needed as part of the course requirements. Google Classroom is one of the applications that is a "instant success" for educators and learners alike, although it challenges with a UI that feels somewhat "clunky." Google Classroom lets teachers organize the digital learning. It tends to improve teaching effectiveness as well as the efficiency of the preparation of lessons. There are instances that students cannot open the uploaded materials due to intermittent to slow internet connectivity and there is no gadget to be used. Others have the gadget and the resources but needs to be mentored on how to use although proper orientation was done already before the opening of classes. But implementing Google Classroom encourages teachers to use a wide range of resources and tasks rather than adhering to a "all are welcome" philosophy, which supports students' learning (Johnson, 2021).

Action is evident in the application of the learnings and skills as proven during midterm and final examination as requirements/culminating activity for the semester's duration. The teacher can give a synchronous or asynchronous examination for the students to do and comply depending on the nature of the course enrolled. However, action is subject to the availability of resources on the part of the students. Interface has something to do with the operation and many of my students have no gadgets to use for online class and they prefer printed module. Although they lack the resources to do so, there is interest in learning how to game the system. This is demonstrated by a study by Ruben et al. (2021), which found that those who used technology more actively (by publishing information, for example) felt that their nonverbal decoding skills were greater, despite performing worse on objective tests of decoding ability. On objective tests of nonverbal decoding ability, however, passive users fared noticeably better, suggesting a possible road map for exploring the connection between usage of technology and interpersonal communication abilities.

According to Biocca and Delaney (2013), a communication interface is a connection between physical media, software, and information and the user's perceptual channels. According to Kay, creating the delusion is the same as creating the interface because it is the relationship between what the consumer sees on the display and what they believe they are manipulating (or, to put it another way, between what the consumers visualizes as well as the user's inner model of action). In essence, the interface consists of the user's "mental image" of the operating system and the machine's "understanding"

of the consumer in equal measure to its physical and visual manifestations. As a result, the interface can be thought of as the expressive space where the consumer and designer collide (Laurel). As a result, what the agent does appears to be "real" since both the user and the creator are in agreement about the "truth" of the depiction it embodies.

Intention, action and impact are the gaps in interpersonal communication found in interface determination.

Quality of Education Analysis

This is an analysis on the quality of education making use of student's outputs and submissions in the Google Classroom to identify the gaps of interpersonal communication in a paragraph discourse analysis.

The quality of education, particularly the caliber of the students' supplied outputs, projects, performance tasks, and assessment criteria, is one of the challenges that has shaken academia throughout this epidemic. With so many alternatives to pick from and everything available with a single click, the internet offers all that is needed for the various courses. However, technology also has the best applications to combat plagiarism of anything simply copied and detects the sources online to validate and verify the works and submissions of students. Still the teacher has the final decision in a student's submission once proven to be a product of cheating. Students are still worried about their marks and the quality of their papers during this pandemic, just as they were during in person orientation. The time limit is the only distinction. The majority of instructors don't set submission deadlines so that students don't have to worry about them, can manage their schedules with other classes they are taking, and can take responsibility for their mental well-being while coping with the contagious and dangerous illness that is a serious health issue.

According to a study by Freeman and Acena (2021), developing interpersonal connections in a more subtle, immersive, and embodied manner may be facilitated by innovative and original social interaction venues that provide expensive-fidelity and multifaceted physical presence. By offering light on how individuals meet, communicate, and build connections with others in comparison to other types of mediums, the study helps us comprehend mediated encounters that are interactive.

Intention plays a crucial role in the students' lives especially in communication. There is an intention to continue studying however due to economic status, students cannot support the needs and demands of the education process vis-à-vis the pandemic hits hard. Ambition is remarkable but is difficult to achieve especially with the challenges and requirements of the courses enrolled as to the nature of the subjects. However, there are students who excelled in classes with remarkable skills and talents shown by overwhelming efforts in the submissions, still quality of education is attained even at a very challenging time. The students exhibit good grades as stipulated in the grades in the Google Classroom even to uploaded grades in the portal. Thus, if there is a will, there is a way to attain quality education even in a challenging time of pandemic.

Action is shown in collaboration and efforts exerted in the outputs submitted and turned in the Google Classroom. It can be seen in the number of turned in outputs as submissions in the Google Classroom. The teacher is not indicating the deadline of submission for consideration purposes to those with intermittent to slow internet connectivity. Students' actions are manifested in early submissions as well as the quality of outputs submitted. The teacher can easily locate students with missing submissions and contact directly the concerned for reminder purposes. A day ahead the scheduled time for submission, a student receives an email reminding them to submit the required output and to dismiss it once it has been submitted and there is no new work due. However, during the wake of the global epidemic, the deadline was disregarded in favor of meeting all of the students' needs. Due to the lack of a device or an internet connection in their location, some students actually called the instructor for interactive lessons.

Impact is manifested in the engagement through the student's effort rendered and consistency exerted to the different requirements of the course as to their grade. In terms of grading the submissions in the Google Classroom, students are made aware of the guidelines, mechanics and rubrics to be used in the giving of grades. The students also receive notification of the scores from the teachers through email and that will also appear in the Google Classroom. The teacher can also send a private message to the student as comments and reactions to the submission as well as suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the work.

Google Classroom enhances the way teachers and students collaborate to deliver high-quality instruction by: (1) raising the level of instructor-learner engagement; (2) streamlining and organizing the classroom; and (3) facilitating learner-educator interaction and cooperation. Google Classroom gives teachers more flexibility to create engaging, interactive classes. Teachers can design assignments that incorporate an engaging YouTube video, a virtual game, or a visually appealing slideshow packed with useful data and photos. Google Classroom engages today's tech-savvy students by making learning enjoyable. Anywhere, at any time, teachers can access student work. On-the-go grade. Having access to every one of the students' assignments and grades is possible from any location at any time using a computer, tablet device, or phone. By offering a single location for assignments, ratings, and announcements, Google Classroom also aids with organization. Everything is simple to locate. All of the completed homework is kept in the Classroom Drive folders and are easily accessible, making it much simpler to find a specific student's work. Teachers may quickly arrange announcements and seek questions. Simply post a message or question on the class stream, and students who log in at the earliest opportunity will see it. Apps for conference calls via video, like Google Meet, make it easier for parents, students, and teachers to communicate from the comfort of their homes or places of business. Video conferencing can come to the rescue if the teacher and pupils are unable to interact in person by hosting virtual parents' conferences, live courses, or a Q&A session (Lynch, 2020).

The interpersonal gap found in the quality of education analysis are intention in communication, action in collaboration and impact in engagement.

A Guideline in Interpersonal Communication in Google Classroom

This guideline helps the teachers and students using Google Classroom as the protocol in the teaching and learning process.

1. **Be respectful.** Respect begets respect. Respect your teacher and your classmates. Put yourself in their shoes. Respect each other's bandwidth.
2. **Be punctual.** Be in the virtual room 5 minutes before the scheduled time whether synchronous or asynchronous.
3. **Be humble.** Accept criticisms, comments, suggestions and recommendations about your submitted outputs for your growth and development.
4. **Be honest.** Tell your teacher the status of your internet connection and signal as your delayed submissions.
5. **Be openminded.** Tell what is in your mind. Ask questions. Tell your story to be understood. Everything is understandable if granted.
6. **Be teachable.** Listen to others because you do not know everything and they too have their stories to tell.
7. **Be kind.** Be always ready to do whatever is asked. Give what you can and do what you can do. It is free but it pays.
8. **Be helpful.** Be always willing to help your struggling classmates about the subject. No man is an island.
9. **Be thankful.** Show gratefulness for the space for learning, the time spent with the teacher and your classmates.
10. **Be yourself.** Be confident in yourself. Trust yourself that you can do.

A ten-guideline list is offered to be used in the teaching and learning process in the Google Classroom.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigates the gaps of interpersonal communication between the teacher and the students in Google Classroom by considering medium, interface and quality of education as sub-problems of the study. Drawing inferences from empirical evidences is done to demonstrate understanding of the problems under study. Finally, a guideline in interpersonal communication in Google Classroom is crafted.

The salient findings of the study are: the gaps in interpersonal communication found in medium identification are intention, action and impact; intention, action and impact are the gaps in interpersonal communication found in interface determination; the interpersonal gaps found in the quality of education analysis are intention in communication, action in collaboration and impact in engagement and a ten-guideline list is offered to be used in the teaching and learning process in the Google Classroom.

The study is a mirror to teachers that there are things uncontrollable specifically interpersonal communication in the Google Classroom even in other educational platforms that needs attention and to be addressed properly because it might hinder teaching effectiveness and learning on the part of the students. Also, it affects the quality

of education as reflected in the academic performance. Teachers should verify the ability of the students to manipulate the interface as a medium of instruction and most importantly the accessibility to wireless fidelity (wi-fi) in the locality.

Google Classroom is a student-friendly application and is accessible even in weak signal and internet connectivity. It is really designed to be such but things there are students who are shy and not confident enough to confide what they are going through in life. Also, with the rampant use of Google application, the teacher needs to be vigilant in the submitted original outputs and just verbatimly copied from online sources.

This study is a reminder that teacher's job is to make the students feel at home in a particular subject even in an online classroom and a smooth communication is assured and insured for better and meaningful teaching and learning process. For future sake, medium identification may be explored in the teaching and learning process in the virtual classrooms as a gap in interpersonal communication; interface determination/operation may be investigated as hindrance/gap in interpersonal communication in virtual classrooms; quality of education may be analyzed and its impact to students learning in virtual classrooms as a gap in interpersonal communication; and an action plan may be crafted to focus on medium identification, interface determination, quality of education and its impact to students learning.

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